

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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Versions

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Method responsible: Matthias Wietz

1 Description of sampling gear

This SOP applies to the autonomous collection of seawater and sinking particles over entire annual cycles via moored, automated devices (Figure 1). This work will establish year-round inventories of the Biological Carbon Pump in the WOBE area. Per sampling event, Remote Access Samplers (RAS gen3, McLane USA; [see manual](#)) automatically collect 500 mL of seawater from the mixed layer (approx. 40-50m depth) in pre-programmed intervals into Kynar® bags (catalog number KYN-500) containing 700 μ L of saturated mercuric chloride solution (7.5%). The RAS tubing is acid-rinsed after each sampling event. Sediment traps (K/MT 234, KUM Germany; [see manual](#)) collect sinking particles over pre-programmed intervals (15-30 days depending on the season) in mesopelagic water layers (1000-3000 m) into vials containing 400 mL artificial seawater containing 8 mL of saturated mercuric chloride solution. For both RAS and traps, the chemical fixation preserves the sample until eDNA analyses after recovery. Autonomous sampling operations have been well established over multiple years in the Arctic FRAM Observatory [1–3], ensuring consistent results under safe handling and negligible risks. Moorings are furthermore equipped with sensor packages for continuous measurements of temperature, salinity, density, chlorophyll fluorescence, and nitrate concentrations (Table 1).

Moored autonomous samplers & sensors:
Microbiology and biogeochemistry across seasons

Figure 1: Autonomous Remote Access Sampler (left) and sediment trap (middle). Devices are deployed on year-round moorings together with sensor packages attached below (right).

Secondly, permanently installed in the bow of Polarstern, is the AUTOFIM autonomous underway filtration system. In intervals of 100 nautical miles, this system will automatically pump seawater from the ship’s intake (~10m depth) and capture microbes on polycarbonate filters.

2 Sampling gear deployment

2.1 Deployment

Mooring operations are done on the main working deck using the large aft crane. Work will be done under strict safety rules (wearing helmets, no walking under running wires and heavy weights). A dedicated mooring technician is always onboard, and works closely with the experienced crew.

RAS, traps and sensors have been deployed in early 2025 within secondary user proposal “SeaCaT” (GPF 24-1/029) at 66° 28,910' S 0° 02,884' E as well as 65° 43,100' S 36° 37,749' W. On the WOBEK expedition PS152, these will be recovered. In case of future WOBEK missions, new deployments are envisioned at similar locations under a deployment / recovery cycle every 2-3 years, in alignment and cooperation with the AWI-HAFOS program and the FRAM Observatory. The average ship time per mooring deployment and recovery are 7h and 9h, respectively (including reference CTD casts). All parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Instrument parameters

Instrument	Sample / data type	Sampling interval / volume
Remote Access Sampler	Water & eDNA	Weekly / 500mL
Sediment trap	Particles & eDNA	Biweekly to monthly / 200mL
CTD sensor	Temperature / salinity / density	Continuously
ECO Triplet sensor	Chlorophyll	Continuously
SUNA / ISUS sensor	Nitrate	Continuously
AUTOFIM	Water & eDNA	Every 100nm / 4L

2.2 Calibration

Sensors on moorings are calibrated in collaboration with AWI sections Physical Oceanography and Biogeochemistry prior to the expedition; all equipment is brought to the ship in ready form. RAS and traps are carefully maintained and prepared in the home lab.

2.3 Post-Deployment

Recovered instruments are rinsed with seawater, and samples removed. Mercuric chloride-poisoned samples are carefully handled using laboratory safety measures (gloves, safety goggles). Samples are immediately placed at 4°C, minimizing any exposure. We require approximately 10m³ of container space to store the equipment, until unloading in the home port.

2.4 Common Issues

The team has ample experience in the handling of moored instruments, founding on years of autonomous sampling in the Arctic Ocean.

3 Sample sorting-collection-preservation procedure

Samples are permanently preserved (i.e. killing all biological activity) by the mixing with mercuric chloride. The sampling containers are closed after recovery and stored as-is at 4°C. This minimizes any potential exposure to mercuric chloride, yet does not affect subsequent molecular and biogeochemical analyses. AUTOFIM samples are collected on polycarbonate filters, and stored at -20C.

4 Sample analysis method

All molecular work and bioinformatic analyses occur in the home institution, within approx. 6 months after recovery. Preserved samples from RAS and traps are processed using established procedures, as outlined in [1-2]. Briefly, RAS water samples are filtered onto 0.22 Sterivex cartridges and DNA extracted using the PowerWater kit. Prior, a 50 mL aliquot has been withdrawn for quantification of nitrate, phosphate and silicate. Trap particle samples are split into several subsamples for biogeochemical measurements (e.g. POC, biogenic silica) as well as DNA extraction using the PowerWater kit. All DNA extracts are amplicon-sequenced using primers targeting prokaryotes, microeukaryotes, and metazoans – resulting in microbial biodiversity inventories in seasonal and environmental

dimensions (relative abundances). Details about sample handling and processing are found in [4]. The workflow for microbial biodiversity assessments is [described here](#).

The resulting biomolecular sequence data will be submitted in raw form to the **European Nucleotide Archive**. In addition, the data will be stored on the AWI Server / Tape Archive, and sample IDs shared within WOBECC along with instructions for access. Sensor data will be submitted to PANGAEA. All data is made available within the WOBECC consortium immediately. Public access will follow after a maximum of two years after sampling, enabling FAIR science. All bioinformatic code will be deposited at Github and Zenodo for full reproducibility.

5 References

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